

Training Centre in Communication
Train. Support. Empower

African Open Science Perspectives Through Strategic Partnerships & Its Impact on Global Dynamics on Responsible Research

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- Executive

Director

@ tcc africa

About us

TCC Africa is an award-winning Trust, established as a non-profit entity in 2006. We provide capacity support in improving researchers output and visibility through training in scholarly and science communication.

Our Mission

Contribute to the increase in profile, locally, and internationally, of African science, and its impact on the life of Africans, by improving skills in technical communication in all forms, at academia and other relevant forums, in Africa.

Our Values

Collaborative

Supportive

Goal -Oriented

Our Objectives

Train. Support. Empower.

Researchers through capacity in improving their research output and visibility.

Institutional Capacity Strengthening

Education

Facilitation

Partnership

Trends

African Research Output 2012-2023

➔ **1,160,159**

OPEN ACCESS

➔ **590,830**

50.9%

Our Capacity Building Ecosystem

Library & Information Literacy Excellence

Upgrade Libraries

Supporting libraries in transitioning to latest Open Science academic publishing technology using FAIR principles

Adoption of Open Science

Education & Awareness

Educate, facilitate and create partnerships on Open Access to raise the profile of African research

Journal Selection Strategy

Advance Scholarship

Smart strategies in mitigating predatory publishing.
Adoption of use of preprints
Increase global credibility, Indexing, ranking & Impact on international communities of knowledge, commerce & public policy.

Higher Education Excellence for Sustainable Economic Development

Strengthen Knowledge Economies

Integrate higher education with industry & public policy to increase economic growth & sustainable development.

Research Excellence

Maximize Research

Improve the quality, quantity, visibility & impact of institutional research.

Higher Education Leadership Excellence

Increase Ranking

Assess, develop & Implement strategies to improve institutional quality, leading to higher global ranking.

Strategic Open Science Partnerships

Dimensions

Kenya

Ghana

Malawi

Uganda

Zambia

Sudan

Namibia

Nigeria

Lesotho

Senegal

Democratic
Republic of Congo

Zimbabwe

Tanzania

Strategic Open Science Partnerships

Dimensions

[Association of African Universities](#)

[African Journals Online](#)

[AfricArxiv](#)

OPEN ACCESS

Select African Developments

Policy

ASSOCIATION OF AFRICAN UNIVERSITIES
ASSOCIATION DES UNIVERSITES AFRICAINES
اتحاد الجامعات الأفريقية

EAST AFRICAN COMMUNITY
EAST AFRICAN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
COMMISSION (EASTECO)

Policy Dialogue

TCC Africa and PLOS are partners in our mission to build and increase Open Science Dialogue at Regional and National Level.

Policy Dialogue

Regional Policy.

EAST AFRICAN COMMUNITY
EAST AFRICAN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
COMMISSION (EASTECO)

For Research & Education Networking

Policy Dialogue

**Institutional Open Science
Mandates**

**Regional
Meetings
Tanzania, Egypt**

Senate Meetings

**ASSOCIATION OF AFRICAN UNIVERSITIES
ASSOCIATION DES UNIVERSITES AFRICAINES
اتحاد الجامعات الأفريقية**

Policy Dialogue

Influential University Policy actors

BOTSWANA INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY
OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

National Dialogues

UNIVERSITEIT VAN PRETORIA
UNIVERSITY OF PRETORIA
YUNIBESITHI YA PRETORIA

Denkleiers • Leading Minds • Dikgopolo tša Dihlalefi

Repositories

TCC Africa and Figshare are partners in our mission to support African College and University Libraries to transition to the adoption of the latest Open Science technologies and FAIR principles, in order to increase the profile, locally and internationally, of African science, and its impact on the life of Africans.

Figshare is supporting capacity building by increasing research output and visibility

	Picked up by 442 news outlets
	Blogged by 13
	Tweeted by 29400
	On 18 Facebook pages
	Reddited by 26
	Highlighted by 1 platforms
	On 10 videos
	196 readers on Mendeley

[See more details](#)

- Figshare allows individual researchers to freely and FAIRly, upload, share, access, store and get credit for all their research outputs.
- Working with sister organizations, **Altmetric and Dimensions**, outputs in Figshare have visible bibliometric information including citations and alternative metrics.
- User-friendly metadata creation, encouraging **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)** research outputs.

Figshare are UNESCO Global Open Science partners

"Figshare's efforts to not only share and store but also enable citations for the range of scientific knowledge products are a valuable contribution to the global effort for open science. We acknowledge these efforts as contributing to the pillar of open scientific knowledge, but also to the transformation of research assessment based on a more comprehensive and equitable framework."

**Ms. Shamila Nair-Bedouelle,
Assistant Director General for Natural Sciences,
UNESCO**

showcase your institution's research outputs in one place

figshare.com @figshare

Part of **DIGITAL** science

Figshare on Africa for Africa

Figshare contributes to AfricArXiv, the Pan-African open access repository which collects research outputs:

- by African researchers
- non-African researchers working on African topics

Figshare provides equitable pricing, using the same country categories (A&B) as the Research4Life programme, as set by the World Bank

Research data sovereignty (Figshare.com)

- Complying with foreign funding mandates can often mean African researchers are passing over our data to the global North. *'Helicopter science.'*
- Figshare enables researchers to get free **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** for their uploaded content, making it trackable, citable, discoverable and easily shareable.
- This helps researchers take ownership of their own research journeys with the proficient infrastructure required and increases the profile of African science.

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DataCite ▼

Science, Digital; Goodey, Gregory; Hahnel, Mark; Zhou, Yuanchun; Jiang, Lulu; Chandramouliswaran, Ishwar; et al. (2022): The State of Open Data 2022. Digital Science. Report. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21276984.v5> [Copy citation](#)

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21276984.v5> [Copy DOI](#)

Thought leadership activities for library literacy

In 2023, Figshare aims to provide support and guidance to increase library literacy with the objectives of embracing the FAIR and CARE principles when it comes to effective research data management. Topics will include:

- Open data
- FAIR principles
- CARE principles
- Research sovereignty and the debate on the authorization of sharing data

The Figshare community in South Africa

Walter Sisulu University

Stellenbosch University

University of Cape Town

University of South Africa

University of Pretoria

Mangosuthu University
of Technology (MUT)

University of the Western
Cape

University of the Free
State

University of Fort Hare

University of
Johannesburg

Sefako Makgatho Health
Sciences University

North-West University

University of KwaZulu-
Natal

Nelson Mandela
University

Rhodes University

Cape Peninsula
University of Technology

<https://knowledge.figshare.com/in/south-africa>

showcase your institution's research outputs in one place

figshare.com @figshare

Collaborating with TENET

Working in collaboration with Figshare, TENET supports libraries wishing to adopt Data and Institutional Repositories in South Africa.

TENET works directly with the South African Universities, to promote the implementation of Figshare repository infrastructure and support procurement in the local currency.

This collaboration provides a successful model that could be replicated across other African nations.

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Part of **DIGITAL**science

AfricArXiv is a community-led digital archive for African research, working towards building an African-owned open scholarly repository; a knowledge commons of African scholarly works

Interventions

Map includes organizational, governmental and international repositories.

It also maps the interactions between research repositories.

African Digital Research Repositories: Mapping the Landscape

I n t e r v e n t i o n s

Why is this important?

Improve the discoverability of African research and publications

Enhance the interoperability of existing and emerging African repositories

Identify ways through which digital scholarly search engines can enhance the discoverability of African research

Resource to be used in activities addressing the following aims:

AfricArxiv

Preprints

We partner with established scholarly repository services to provide a platform for African scientists of any discipline to present their research findings and connect with other researchers on the African continent and globally.

tabular data, images, video,
presentations, posters,
code, book chapters

manuscripts,
posters,
presentations

manuscripts, posters,
presentations, audio/visual

manuscripts,
reviews/commentaries,
scholarly definitions

manuscripts

tabular data, images, video,
presentations, posters,
code, book chapters

Select Concerns

“Insufficient engagement on Open Science to leadership in universities (especially when it comes to research, promotions, incentives, competitiveness, using preprints, and matters relating to Intellectual Property Rights as compared to Open Access (publishing and open books)”

“Little awareness on Open science among higher education institute administrators”

“Poor attitude towards Open Science/Open Access”

“The perception that “free” means low quality.”

“Lack of mindset change by open science contributors”

Select Recommendations

“Enact workable and implementable policies to promote open science”

“Investing in developing facilities and technology that promote open science”

“Count for promotion”

“Award and recognition for outstanding researchers”

“The copyright and common license initiatives should be well -developed and spelled out”

Let's Connect

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in

